

Studies on Adsorption of Chromate as Inhibitor for Mild Steel in Aqueous Solution of Mixture of Aggressive Ions

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The application of corrosion inhibitors, specially in the closed systems, holds a prominent place amongst other protective methods. Chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions are aggressive from corrosion point of view¹. As an inhibitor chromate has been used for iron in neutral and weakly alkaline media² and for mild steel in alcohol solution³. For mild steel, chromate as inhibitor in aqueous solution of chloride, sulphate, nitrate⁴ and in mixture of chloride and sulphate⁵ has been reported earlier.

In the present study an attempt has been made to study the behaviour and mechanism of adsorption of chromate as corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in aqueous solution of mixture of sodium chloride and sodium sulphate.

Results and Discussion

The mixture of 60 parts (by vol) sodium chloride and 40 parts (by vol) sodium sulphate (both $10^{-1} M$) being most corrosive for mild steel⁵, was selected for further studies. The results of effect of temperature (20–80°) on the corrosion of mild steel are shown in Table 1 along with activation energy (E_a) of corrosion reaction (calculated from Arrhenius plots, log corrosion vs $1/T$). With rise in temperature, the corrosion rate increases and the increased efficiency of the inhibitor may be due to increased adsorption⁶ of chromate enabling the formation of a protective passive film⁷. At higher temperatures, the rates of adsorption and desorption depend on the kinetic property of the molecule in solution. Probably the equilibrium shifts towards higher adsorption for time so that the metal surface remains covered for longer duration towards medium and thus corrosion is decreased even at higher temperature⁸. The adsorption of inhibitor molecules causes an increase in the E_a (which increases with inhibitor concentration) of the process and the increase is proportional to the extent of adsorption⁹.

To examine the adsorption behaviour of the inhibitor, the data has been fitted to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm,

$$C/\theta = 1/K + C$$

where, K is the equilibrium constant for adsorption process, θ the surface coverage and C the concentration of inhibitor. A plot of C/θ vs C is a straight-line supporting the Langmuir adsorption. The values of surface coverage (θ) and other thermodynamic parameters like heat of ad-

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE CORROSION OF MILD STEEL IN $10^{-1} M$ NaCl AND Na_2SO_4 MIXTURE CONTAINING K_2CrO_4

Temp. °C	Weight-loss (mg dm ⁻²)*			
	NaCl + Na_2SO_4	NaCl + Na_2SO_4 + 0.03% K_2CrO_4	NaCl + Na_2SO_4 + 0.05% K_2CrO_4	NaCl + Na_2SO_4 + 3% K_2CrO_4
20	48.29	10.06	7.72	Nil
	–	(79.16)	(84.04)	(100.00)
40	69.33	12.76	10.91	Nil
	–	(81.50)	(84.29)	(100.00)
60	102.08	17.14	13.63	Nil
	–	(83.20)	(88.64)	(100.00)
80	241.39	34.06	22.71	Nil
	–	(85.89)	(90.59)	(100.00)
E_a , KJ mol ⁻¹	11.69	16.35	29.23	–

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF θ , ΔG , ΔS AND Q AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN $10^{-1} M$ SOLUTION OF MIXTURE OF NaCl AND Na_2SO_4

Temp. °C	θ	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Q kJ mol ⁻¹
20	0.8491	21.09	98.37	
40	0.8426	22.58	96.86	
60	0.8664	24.56	96.98	7.73
80	0.9100	27.00	98.38	

sorption (Q), free energy of adsorption (ΔG) and entropy of adsorption (ΔS) (Table 2) were calculated as done earlier¹⁰. The negative free energy for adsorption shows strong interaction of inhibitor molecule¹¹ and spontaneous adsorption on the metal surface¹². The increase in free energy of adsorption with temperature indicates the increase in inhibitor efficiency with temperature¹⁰ (as found in this case also). Relatively small value of heat of adsorption indicates that the adsorption of inhibitor occurs easily and may be of physical type¹³. Increase in E_a in presence of inhibitor and small values of ΔG are also indicative of physical adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface¹⁴.

Chromate inhibits corrosion by masking the active sites of metal surface due to the surface adsorption which follows Langmuir adsorption isotherm. Strong interaction of inhibitor on the corroding metal surface is accomplished by the negative free energy. Small values of heat of ad-

sorption and free energy of adsorption with increase in activation energy in presence of inhibitor suggest that the inhibitor may be physically adsorbed on the metal surface.

Experimental

Mild steel specimens (C, 0.25; Mn, 0.47; Si, 0.089; S, 0.049; P, 0.042%) of the size 5 × 2.5 cm (thickness 18 SWG) were degreased with carbon tetrachloride, washed with benzene and dried. Other experimental details were the same as described earlier¹⁵.

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